

**BIM: IMPROVING COLLABORATIVE WORKING
DURING PPP/PFI PROJECT LIFECYCLE**

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Declaration:

I hereby confirm that this dissertation is my own work.

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Statement of Authorship

I Miguel Ângelo Camelo Ferrão Moreira, confirm that this work submitted for assessment is my own and is expressed in my own words. Any uses made within it of the works of other authors in any form (e.g. ideas, equations, figures, text, tables, programmes) are properly acknowledged at the point of their use. Full list of the references employed has been included.

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Abstract

The construction industry has witnessed many changes in the last few years. Projects are becoming increasingly challenging and the more competitive economical environment is forcing construction companies and clients to find new synergies to react quickly and effectively to these challenges. Therefore, collaborative work is becoming very important to the successful delivery of construction projects. PPP/PFI contracts are becoming the procurement choice to deliver public projects. These procurement agreements englobe the whole life cycle of projects and involve a great number of stakeholders. Consequently, pressure is put on collaborative work and companies look for ways of enhancing it. Technologies such as BIM can provide a platform for stakeholders to access and share information, improve design visualization and work practices that promote collaborative working. The aim of this research is to investigate how BIM can improve collaborative work in PPP/PFI project lifecycle. A literature review to appraise collaborative work and review lifecycles of PPP/PFI revealed issues that were investigated through a questionnaire survey on the UK construction industry. Although, the number of responses collected is not representative for the industry, the survey reached a variety of professionals and could conclude that BIM has a positive effect on collaborative work. Accordingly, the research found that the initial investment, top management support and industry reluctance to change are the three major barriers to implement BIM. This thesis concludes by recommending clients to incorporate funds in there budgets to support the initial investment and help changing the perception of top management through BIM.

Keywords: Construction industry, collaborative work, PPP/PFI, projects lifecycle, BIM.

Glossary of Abriviations

PPPs	Public Private Partnerships
BIM	Building Information Modelling
SCM	Supply Chain Management
DBB	Design-Bid-Build
DB	Design-Build
PPP	Public Private Partnership
PFI	Public Finance Initiative
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
BIM	Building Information Modelling
SPV	Special Purpose Vehicle
VfM	Value for Money
IT	Information Technology
3D	Three-Dimensional
BIM 4D	Schedule
BIM 5D	Estimatinion

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Rationale

There is a consensus in the construction industry that in order to remain competitive new work methodologies need to be introduced to meet the demanding requirements of clients. The current economic environment and challenging projects are putting the construction industry under pressure to respond quickly and efficiently to these challenges. Construction projects are known for the involvement of many stakeholders during its life cycle that have to work together to design, build and operate the asset. For these reasons a collaborative work environment is important for the delivery of a successful project and has been recognised as a critical success factor for managing construction projects (Xue et al., 2010). Poor collaboration is a source of many problems of the industry, can put at risk the success of a project resulting in time and cost overruns. Therefore, companies are always looking to new ways of implementing effective collaboration strategies.

During the 1990s a new procurement arrangement emerged called Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) and since then they have been the procurement route of choice for many countries worldwide. According to EPEC (2012) the United Kingdom is one of the largest markets for PPPs with more than 550 contracts in 2010 spanning a wide range of sectors worth over £46 billion. This procurement route has a great impact on collaborative work environment since the private sector absorbs most of the risk. It is in the consortium's best interest to cooperate and collaborate to solve any project problems that might arise; another reason is the long term contractual arrangement that is valid throughout the whole project's life cycle. In such projects the success depends on considerations of the life cost, and the right balance of construction cost and running cost is needed. To achieve this balance all the internal stakeholders from the designer, contractor, and facilities manager must work together and collaborate effectively. Although, PPPs projects have improved time and budget certainty and the delivery of high quality assets and services throughout the life cycle of projects, many cases have failed to deliver value for money to the tax payer (HM Treasury, 2012).

Building Information Modelling (BIM) can assist internal stakeholders to evaluate assets in a 3D virtual environment and collaboratively work to find solutions that enhance the project and deliver value for money to the taxpayer. According to the Cabinet Office (2011) BIM provides a shared work platform where alternative designs can be evaluated, coordination errors be eliminated and improve communication with the supply chain. As a result, from 2016 on BIM must be implemented on government projects. This technology can be an effective tool to improve working practices and enhance collaboration among the project's team.

1.2 Aims and Objectives

The purpose of this research is to evaluate how BIM can improve collaborative working during the whole life cycle of a PPP/PFI contract arrangement.

Specific objectives aligned with the aim are listed below:

1. To critically appraise collaborative working in construction;
2. To review whole life cycle of a project delivered by PPP/PFI contract and advantages introduced by BIM;
3. To evaluate BIM as a collaborative working enabler in PPP/PFI projects;
4. To provide recommendations to support the implementation of BIM.

1.3 Hypothesis

The dissertation hypothesis is “collaborative working during the whole life cycle of the PPP/PFI agreement will be enhanced due to the introduction of BIM”

1.4 Research Methodology

To test the research hypothesis two methodologies were employed. First, a desk study, an extensive and comprehensive literature review on the subject. This study focused on appraising collaborative work in the construction industry. Special attention on investigating PPP/PFI projects lifecycle and the improvements of BIM as an enabler of collaborative working. The information of this study was assessed from construction

research journals and articles, scientific books, government's reports, university journals and articles and online sources on the subject.

Secondly, a survey questionnaire was used to collect data from the UK construction industry. A specific question on the questionnaire selected professionals with the appropriate experience. The objective of the questionnaire was to quantify improvements BIM bring to collaborative work in PPP/PFI projects. Consequently, a quantitative methodology as selected and the data statistically analysed.

In chapter four all the details on the methods used for the research are specified.

1.5 Dissertation Structure

The research is composed of six chapters. Each chapter is divided in subheadings to guide readers and enable a better understanding of the subject. The chapters are divided as follows:

Chapter 1 – An introduction of the research, aims, objectives and the dissertation structure.

Chapter 2 – A literature review on collaborative working in the construction industry. Defines the collaborative working concept, followed by the factors that enable it, such as business, people and technology strategy and the barriers to effective collaborative working.

Chapter 3 – A literature review in PPP/PFI projects. The theoretical background, followed by the concept of collaborative working in PPP/PFI projects, review of project lifecycle and the advantages of BIM in PPP/PFI projects.

Chapter 4 – reviews the various existing research techniques and presents the methodology used to carry out the research.

Chapter 5 – covers the analyses of the data collected and present a discussion on the results of the survey and literature review.

Chapter 6 – presents the conclusions of the research with a summary, limitations and recommendations for further research.

Chapter Two: Collaborative Working in Construction

2.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to critically appraise collaborative work in the construction industry. In order to achieve these aims the following key objectives were established: to define collaborative work; find the key areas that enable collaborative work; investigate the trends and identify barriers to effective collaborative work. There is widespread recognition that the construction industry requires more collaborative work. Fragmentation along the project's whole life cycle can be difficult to manage resulting in an adversarial environment where internal stakeholders work without any motivation to effectively work in collaboration. Instead they pursue only their own aims, in many cases threatening the project goals.

The construction industry competes in an open and extremely competitive market and if companies want to survive they have to find new ways of working in order to be ahead of their competitors. Collaborative working is a key element for companies to improve their performance and improve competitiveness. According to Xue et al. (2010) collaborative working is one of the most critical success factors in construction projects. Greenwood and Wu (2012) suggests that collaborative procurement methods and working practices can improve performance not only in time, cost and quality objectives but also with other general outcomes, such as greater innovation and improved user satisfaction. In recent years, construction has witnessed changes in the way it operates. Technological advances in information and communication technologies, computer-aided design and information management have changed the way people communicate and share information. Furthermore, companies are looking for synergies with their partners in order to improve efficiency and gain competitiveness. For this reason the management paradigm in the construction industry is changing and companies are looking to the best methods of enhancing effective collaborative work in their organisations.

2.2 Definition of Collaborative work

The term collaborative working in the construction industry has been defined in many different ways. The Oxford dictionary (2016) defines “*collaborative*” as “*Produced by or involving two or more parties working together*”. A simple way to define it is the involvement of two or more project stakeholders working together effectively and efficiently towards a common goal (Xue et al., 2010, Patel et al., 2012). Consequently, according to Greenwood and Wu (2012) the industry is misinterpreting this concept and describes collaborative working as “partnering”. Although, the term partnering incorporates a form of collaboration among different organisations it is not a synonym of collaborative work and, in many cases, has been used as a marketing tool to vindicate collaborative working making the analysis of this concept even more relevant (Greenwood and Wu, 2012).

Construction projects are known for involving many stakeholders working together. In order to improve quality, time and cost, companies collaborate together by informal network, alliances, partnering or fully integration to work throughout shared goals and working efficiently and effectively to find solutions that can satisfy all stakeholders (Xue et al., 2010). However, to bringing all these stakeholders together does not ensure that they will work together as a team. Shelbourn et al. (2012) states that the lack of organisation, misunderstanding, poor communication, and inadequate participation can result in problems and difficulties. To enable collaborative working the right environment needs to be establish. Erdogan et al. (2014) approached collaboration environment as an environment produced by the use of different collaboration tools and technologies that enable all the organisations involved in the construction project to communicate, exchange data and information, and drive joint activities to achieve the successful completion of this project. In order to accomplish this environment the organisations need to work effectively. According to Shelbourn et al. (2012) in order to achieve effective collaboration there are three key strategies that need to be carefully aligned in harmony; the business strategy, people strategy, and technology strategy. Six key factors that have to be considered within these strategies to enable effective collaboration: vision, engagement, trust, communication, process, and technology.

Some academics focus on the technological aspect that enable collaborative working whereas, others are focusing on the organisation relationship. The concept of

collaborative working should have a more holistic perspective and consider these three key strategies for a more appropriate definition.

2.3 Factors Enabling Collaborative Work in Construction

2.3.1 Business Strategy

Construction projects have become more complex resulting in the increase of uncertainty and risk (Eriksson and Westerberg, 2011). Furthermore, limitations on people and financial resources are increasing the pressure on internal stakeholders to deliver construction projects and services more efficiently and effectively by eliminating waste and work duplication. In order to ensure that they can achieve their short and long term objectives, many clients are working in a closer relationship throughout their supply chain. With the intention to increase time and cost certainty, improve disputes resolution processes, team work and innovation, many clients are partnering and making use of new contract forms to encourage collaborative work (Constructing Excellence, 2009).

According to Xue et al. (2010) from the point of view of the organisation and work relationship, partnering and alliancing are two types of business strategy in collaborative working and were established to improve adversarial relationship among internal stakeholders. This business strategy generates the conditions for sustainable relationships, better risk management, elimination of work duplication and promote technological innovation throughout the projects life cycle, accomplishing all these through collaborative relationships (Constructing Excellence, 2009, Xue et al., 2010). Partnering and alliancing also play an important role in improving the company's competitive advantage in the global market by sharing skills and resources, combining insights, reduce uncertainties and accelerate learning (Badger and Mulligan, 1995, Xue et al., 2010). However, in many cases, companies are focusing in short-term profit-sharing accountability and do not take fully advantage of the long-term relationship that add value, knowledge and improve performance (Ingirige and Sexton, 2006).

Alliancing and Partnering

There are different forms of business strategies from the relationship point of view. Corporate, project and strategic alliancing and joint venture contracts forces a collaboration relationship. They are used for long-term relationship in inter-organisational arrangements for mutual benefits and to improve corporate competitiveness. Partnering has no contractual standing itself. The key similarity is that they both delivery the results through collaborative work (Anvuur and Kumaraswamy, 2007, Yeung et al., 2007). Another existing business strategy is Supply Chain Management (SCM), this strategy has been used successfully in the manufacturing industry, such as automotive and aerospace sectors. SCM is inseparable from the lean thinking and can be defined as “*coordination of independent enterprises in order to improve the performance of the whole supply chain by considering their individual needs* (Lau et al., 2004)”. Although, SCM is well established in the manufacturing industry the fragmentation and the rootness-in-place of construction projects alongside with industry organisation, poor understanding of the nature of the SCM between partners and the lack of confidence in SCM to improve construction performance makes it less successful in the construction industry (Xue et al., 2010). However, these businesses strategies have great potential to improve collaborative work.

Procurement

Procurement routes are becoming more complex forcing companies into new forms of relationship such as partnering that can create more value. These new relationships are changing the construction industry by introducing attributes like trust and openness that can only be achieved by improving collaborative work.

Working relationships are the key issues in collaborative working and business strategies and is important to incorporate these in the project. Another important issue is the delivery system. Procurement plays a pivotal role on the success of construction projects has an enabler of collaborative working. The procurement route can establish links between the internal stakeholders that are important to create an effective team or reduce cooperation resulting in an adverse environment where everyone work to defend their own interests. In the traditional procurement design-bid-build (DBB) the client specifies the product, then together with consultants prepares a detailed design in order to establish the conditions for a competitive bidding to procure the contractor (Song et

al., 2009, Eriksson and Westerberg, 2011). According to Eriksson (2016.) DBB does not provide sufficient incentive for cooperation resulting in competitive and poor relationships. In addition, the separation of the design, construction and the high level of specifications before the contract being procured results in project delays and decrease in innovation due to an absence of a holistic vision on design, construction and lack of synergy for problem-solving (Eriksson and Westerberg, 2011, Rutten et al., 2009). In design-build (DB) the contract is procured at early stages of the project based on a project brief or sketch drawings. The contractor is responsible for the construction drawing. Due to the early involvement of the contractor better solutions with higher constructability designs can be found (Tam, 2000, Eriksson and Westerberg, 2011). This procurement route enables better collaboration among the internal stakeholders since the contractor is accountable for the design, in many situations contractors look to find synergies with consultants in order to optimise the design by rising the collaborative environment. Although, DB contracts have shown to add more value for money and to improvement time delivery, there are still some disadvantages to take into consideration compared to DBB (Tam, 2000). DB reduces the client influence in the design works and a complete design before completion can improve quality and price performance (Eriksson and Westerberg, 2011, Cheung et al., 2001). For this reason contract clauses evolved to guaranty maximum price options and warranty and novation arrangements were created to transfer design risks to contractors while clients maintain design control (Constructing Excellence, 2009). Nevertheless, Eriksson and Westerberg (2011) concluded that for the design stage more integration between client and contractors will improve performance in terms of cost, time, quality, environmental impact, work environment and innovation making this form of procurement more suitable for complex projects.

Public Private Partnership (PPP) and Public Finance Initiative (PFI)

As DB moved towards more advance formats, government financial constraints meant that finance and operation were incorporated into DB creating PPP/PFI (Constructing Excellence, 2009). These complex advance forms of procurement are long term agreements that run through the whole life cycle of the project and for this reason involve a numerous of internal stakeholders that in order to succeed have to work together increasing the pressure to enable collaborative work.

2.3.2 People Strategy

People and relationship have been recognised as two major factors for collaborative success and the lack of continuity of relationship at company, teams and individual levels can harm the full benefits of collaboration and the transfer of skills throughout the project (Shelbourn et al., 2012). Shelbourn et al. (2012) states that longer-term strategic planning and the mutual advantageous customer-supply relationship are important for collaboration and they are difficult to achieve, maintain and sustain.

The increase in interest from researchers in attitudes and behaviours in construction project environment shows how important this area is. According to Xue et al. (2010) many behavioural factors can affect collaboration. Trust, concern for relationship, incentive, conflict and tension are key behaviour factors that should be taken into consideration. Trust is one of the most studied factors and is widely accepted by researchers as the most important success factor for collaborative working. This factor exists at a personal, organisational and inter-organisational level and can help to integrate partners and openness to information sharing reducing the need for formal contracting (Xue et al., 2010). This factor is so important that Smyth and Edkins (2007) are using it as a measure of relationship conditions in PPP/PFI projects where their success relies heavily on cooperation and collaborative working.

Tension and conflicts are also important factors since they challenge relationships throughout the project. Although conflict in many cases being preconceived as harmful, can also create opportunities for stakeholders to think through ideas, produce high-quality solutions, deliver better performance and improve organisation effectiveness (Hoffman, 1959, Mullins, 2010).

These behaviours must be taken into consideration when teams are put together to share a project. According to Shelbourn and Bouchlaghem (2012) these teams have to be able to work in a reliable manner to build competence, develop interpersonal relationships and perform collectively. In order to help these teams, companies make use of a key employee or “champion” that is responsible to plan and implement effective collaboration. These employees must understand the people and business process, collaborative tools and technologies and the organisation practices and procedures. The “champion” should represent the organisation throughout the collaborative journey as the project manager of the collaborative effort. For this reason attributes of an effective leader and collaborative work experience is needed since the teams will look for

guidance from them. They should help the team to develop a shared vision in order to reduce the risk of conflicts expectation and goals, and also ensure the credibility of the information and effective communication increasing the levels of trust and respect. By doing so the collaborative environment should enhance productivity by focusing attention on the work, encourage both individuals and group interaction, minimise cost for monitoring, and maximise individual and group energy and enthusiasm for the venture (Shelbourn and Bouchlaghem, 2012).

2.3.3 Technology Strategy

Technological solutions have been the focus of collaborative work in the recent years, especial attention is given on web (extranets), computer-aided design and information/knowledge management technologies (Bouchlaghem and Shelbourn, 2012). Some of the merits of the collaborative environment establish by these technologies can be attributed to information and communication technologies (ICT) since they enable the exchange of information between project stakeholders. For this reason ICT improves collaboration in organisations and should be carefully planned and implemented. Collaborative tools such as intranet, extranet, enterprise information portals, knowledge management applications and other can support the exchange of information through a network improving collaboration between different users. Online collaboration through this network can reduce geographical boundaries making use of conferencing systems reducing the need for physical meetings achieving savings in time and resources. There are many available technologies that can be customise to help support specific areas of collaboration (Shelbourn et al., 2012).

Wireless networks, bluetooth networks, mobile communication and cloud storage changed the way peoples communicate facilitating data sharing and storage. According to U.S.Robotics (2016) wireless technology allows multiple computers to share data such as files, videos and network printers simultaneously in a network without wires. Bluetooth networks also allow users to share data wirelessly and without being connected to the internet, however, bluetooth has the disadvantage of a shorter transmission distance (Gao et al., 2012). The mobile technology evolution in the past years as allowed information to be shared remotely almost from any part of the world reducing geographic boundaries. Fourth generation (4G) mobile network has a broadband that allow diverse data to be quickly transferred and assure high quality communication, this system is evolving to 5G that is expected to lead mobile

communications by the year 2020 and enhance users experience (Chen et al., 2015). Cloud storage system is a low cost solution for storing information in a virtual server that can be accessed remotely in real time facilitating users to access and load information and improve collaborative working (Ding and Xu, 2014). The evolution of these communication systems are improving communications and are now an important pillar that supports collaborative work.

Building Information Modelling

During the mid-90s advances on ICT enable the development of new sophisticated CAD systems. These systems allowed to add information such as materials characteristics and costs to improve 3D models. This technology can be referred as building information modelling (BIM). This technology makes it possible to simulate and built any project in a virtual environment, using just a computer and appropriate software. Enabling the designers to experiment, simulate construction and make modifications in the project before physical construction (Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010). Although, BIM is still considered a design tool among many people in the construction industry, this technology can bring benefits throughout the whole life cycle of a construction project. Gu and London (2010) defined BIM as *“an IT enabled approach that involves applying and maintaining an integral digital representation of all building information for different phases of the project lifecycle in the form of a data repository. The building information involved in the BIM approach can include both geometric data as well as non-geometric data”*. Producing and maintaining this information enables collaboration among different stakeholders throughout the whole life cycle of a construction project, since they insert, extract and update the BIM model according to their roles in the project (Ding and Xu, 2014). Ding and Xu (2014) states that BIM ensures accurate and consistent information, solves the problem of information isolation and discontinuity between stakeholders by improving the efficiency of the project life cycle management and enhances company value. For these reasons BIM should be seen as a dynamic process that, by making use of a 3D model with all the project information, can support collaborative work for assisting the clients to understand their needs and the aim of the project through the design stage and allowing an analysis to whole life cycle of the project (Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010). At the design stage BIM can provide a 3D visualization and show the entire asset more intuitively and achieve professional collaborative design (Ding and Xu, 2014).

Designers can communicate their views through the 3D model facilitating the proposals of different approaches by visualising different spaces and aesthetic finishes, enabling customers and designers to easily make the adjustments needed on the project to achieve the desired goals (Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010, Love et al., 2011). BIM used in collaborative design implies that different design specialist use the same 3D model, thus BIM can contribute on coordinating in the design of all these services in such a way that they do not conflict with each other. This process, is known as clash detection, and can bring numerous savings in time and cost during the construction phase (Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010, Azhar et al., 2008). For these reasons integrated functions and information in collaborative design enable smooth communication among the design team improving quality and productivity by preventing unnecessary work (Oh et al., 2015).

Since the 3D model also contains quantitative information it can be linked to a cost database and at this stage estimate the cost based on the model quantities. Consequently, the cost estimation directly linked to the 3D modelling and any change will update the cost estimation (Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010, Cheung et al., 2012). At advance level of collaboration the 3D model can be directly linked to the supply chain and give more realistic estimations.

Another important feature of BIM at this stage is the simulation of the asset during its use. This feature allows the design team to analyse the whole life cost of the asset providing information for alternative designs (Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010, Azhar et al., 2012).

In the construction phase, the construction of the project can be simulated with different construction methods and processes. Making use of 4D construction management (time analysis) that allows integrated dynamic visualisation, it is possible to predict construction time and select the construction method that improves time, cost and quality (Ding and Xu, 2014). Also assembly instructions can be part of the 3D model, forcing the site team to visit the model to find solutions for the assembling of components. Furthermore, the 3D model also can help to solve some of the problems that may arise during this stage. For this reason BIM can become the centre of communication and collaboration between the design team and the construction site (Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010).

In the operation stage, BIM can be used for intelligent management and maintenance of equipment (Ding and Xu, 2014). Nevertheless, it is important that “as built” information is loaded in the 3D model to provide accurate information that enables BIM to be used as an accurate building property management tool (Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010, Azhar et al., 2012).

When the construction industry is looked at, as a whole, one of the biggest problems is the implementation of teamwork and collaboration between internal stakeholders, one reason is the cultural barrier among them. BIM can overpass these barriers since the model is universally accessible by all internal stakeholders resulting in automatic updates of information that all have access in real time (Naoum and Egbu, 2016). Furthermore, BIM can improve the quality and flow of information through the project’s life cycle and promote inter-disciplinary learning and collaboration with the supply chain (Baddeley and Chang, 2015). Also, the relationship with partners is improved since BIM allows more information transparency improving the allocation of responsibility and the decision making process (Grilo et al., 2013). BIM can enhance collaborative working since the input of all members of the project is promoted and an effective communication platform is provided improving the time, cost and quality of construction project.

2.4 Barriers to Effective Collaboration

It is known that collaboration is highly required in the construction industry due to the number of stakeholders involved and of its geographical dispersed project nature, people and relationships are the central point of the collaboration success. There are many collaborative tool and systems that enable collaborative work but, putting people to use them can be difficult and a barrier to effective collaboration (Shelbourn et al., 2012). According to Shelbourn et al. (2012) the causes are a combination of human and management factors including resistance to change due to lack of training and management support for the collaborative tools and technologies. Furthermore, other common barriers to effective collaboration as differing visions from the collaborating organisations with different mission, goals and priorities; different communication methods and organisation culture; lack of focus and consensus on delegating tasks; an imbalance of resources time, money and ; confidentiality, intellectual property and legal

considerations; technological incompatibility; miss understanding the expertise, knowledge and language of the other collaborating participants. Erdogan et al. (2008) found that the barriers are not due to the lack of tools and technology but rather a lack of awareness of how they can be explored and the importance cultural change have in order to allow this process to happen. On their literature survey they found that most of the authors mentioned similar issues with the motive for the implementation of collaborative systems to fail. They grouped into six categories:

1. Poor capture of user requirements;
2. Lack of strategic approaches (lack of alignment between the IT strategy, and organisational strategy, focusing on short term solutions);
3. Lack of proper planning;
4. User resistance to change;
5. Lack of user involvement;
6. Technical characteristics (Erdogan et al., 2008).

In summary, the barriers for effective collaboration, in most cases, originate in the people and the way organisations organise and implement the tools and systems available.

2.5 Conclusion

In order to critically appraise collaborative work in the construction industry, a literature review was carried out to better understand what collaborative work is, the key areas that enable it, and investigate the trends and the barriers to effective collaborative work. The review found that there are three key strategies that enable collaborative work business strategy, people strategy and technology strategy. To achieve effective collaborative work the right balance between all three must be achieved.

The industry is changing and the business and technology strategy are suffering major changes. New trends on the way companies are making business are improving the collaborative environment but at the same time increasing pressure to improve the communication and knowledge sharing. Partnering and alliances are the new trends for companies that aim to increase gains in competitiveness. Advance incorporated procurement routes such as PPP/PFI that incorporate the whole life cycle of the project

are taking collaborative work to a different dimension. In these procurement routes internal stakeholders such as designers, facility managers and contractors need to work in collaboration in order to achieve value for money. Technology is keeping up with this trend, new and faster communication systems have been developed. Never has it been easier to store, share and access information remotely. New computer-aided design technology such as BIM are promising to revolutionise the construction industry, making possible to create a 3D model that can simulate the whole life cycle of a facility. This technology can be used not just to improve the design stage but at the same time improve the construction phase and the service.

The review illustrate that some of the barriers for effective collaborative work are related not with the lack of technology but with people and organisation management supporting the idea that something may be wrong with the people strategy. PPP/PFI projects relay heavily on people and enterprises cooperation and collaboration in order to succeed. The mandatory introduction of BIM level 2 for public sector projects are promising to increase collaborative work among internal stakeholders. The wide utilisation of BIM by different stakeholders along the project life cycle can help to overcome cultural barriers and transform this technology in a powerful enabler for collaborative work. The next chapter reviews the whole life cycle of a PPP/PFI project and the enhancements BIM can bring throughout the different phases, in order to boost collaborative work.

Chapter Three: Public Private Partnership and Project Finance Initiative

3.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to review PPP/PFI contracts and the advances introduced by BIM. In the previous chapter collaborative working in the construction industry was appraised, finding key areas and new trends such as BIM that enable collaborative working. Public private partnerships and public finance initiatives (PPP/PFI) contracts are integrated and advance formats of procurement that for their nature and long term arrangement enable collaboration among internal stakeholders. For this reason the tools, techniques, and technology appraised in the first chapter in these procurement formats are challenged and also key success factor to achieve the project goals.

With the end of the financial crisis the UK government committed to make vast investments in infrastructures. Some of these investments are going to be delivery by PPP/PFI contracts since this procurement route is becoming more important around the world accounting already for 10% of the total investments in the UK (Be, 2003). Some of these projects have been successful while others have failed (Liu et al., 2015). In the UK criticism to these procurement routes are increasing because some opponents advocate that they do not provide value for money to taxpayers (Love et al., 2015). Value for money is the critical decision factor for choosing this procurement route. The long-term agreement can last between 10 to 40 years where the private sector is responsible for designing, construct, operate and maintain the procured asset. For this reason the project must be well defined and the whole life cycle cost taken into consideration to ensure project success and value for money to the taxpayer. Therefore, the team needs to effectively work in collaboration from the beginning of the project in order to take the right design decisions with buildability, operation and maintenance in mind to forecast the project costs as a whole. The high numbers of internal stakeholders involved in the project must collaborate effectively throughout the project and technology such as BIM can improve collaboration and be an effective solution to manage the project throughout its life cycle, as shown in the previous chapter.

3.2 Background

In the last two decades fiscal constraints forced governments to adopt new procurement strategies. In order to increase investments without exceeding prescribed public debts limits imposed by the European Union and the UK Chancellor's "golden economical rule" that impose sanctions to governments that exceed deficit limits, Private Finance Initiatives (PFI) became the primary policy to procure construction projects. Later on a change in the procurement policy allow governments to contract services by directly finance the capital expenditure for some projects changing the policy to Public Private Partnerships (PPP) (Smyth and Edkins, 2007).

The procedure in a PFI starts with a creation of a company called special purpose vehicle (SPV), which is responsible for the whole project. All the risks of the design, construction and commissioning of the contracted asset are transferred to the SPV (Oyegoke et al., 2009). The UK government is one of the pioneers of these procurement routes, the duration of the concession contracts can fluctuate between 10 and 40 years. These contracts can supply a range number of services, including IT and facility management. The contracts can include build-own-operate-transfer different facilities such as schools, hospitals and prisons where the SPV is responsible for providing and servicing the assets during the years of concession. In return the government reimburse a series of payments or rent to the SPV, for providing these services, instead of the initial capital cost. Project participants include the client from the public sector and the SPV members, the last include all the stakeholders involved not just in the construction of the asset but the ones involved during the whole life cycle of the project, including the management company with members from all the organisations that constitute the SPV, namely contractors, operating companies responsible for the functional service supplied, maintenance and facility management and in the case of PFI a debt and equity financier (Smyth and Edkins, 2007).

Another important reason public clients are procuring construction services throughout PFI/PPP procurement routes is that they offer greater value for money (VfM). This expression is used to translate how economy, efficiency and effectiveness public sectors bodies are operating (Clifton and Duffield, 2006). According to Clifton and Duffield (2006) the major factors that should be taking into consideration measuring value for money in a PPP/PFI contract are: risk transfer; whole of life costing; innovation (financial, structural, service and technical); asset utilisation; output based specification;

performance measurement and incentives; and capturing of private sector management skills (Clifton and Duffield, 2006). However, PPP/PFI also have disadvantages that need to be addressed. These procurement routes have higher financial costs since, has inflexibility structure that make future changes almost impossible and the negotiations are slower and costly (Price Water House Coopers, 2005).

Although most of the risk of these procurement arrangements is transferred to the SPV during the concession contract, collaborative work is needed to improve the commercial management of this risk. For this reason all the tools that enhance the collaborative environment throughout this process are going to bring more value for money.

3.3 Collaborative Work in PPP/PFI

PPP/PFI contracts are long-term agreements that involve many stakeholders with different objectives and for this reason require flexibility to guarantee the delivery of services throughout the full duration of the agreement (Clifton and Duffield, 2006). Therefore, this agreements take collaboration beyond limits of the contract, and effective relationship between the members of the SPV and between SPV and public client should be well established during this agreement to enable the success of the project (Smyth and Edkins, 2007).

PPP/PFI projects helped to develop awareness and expertise in whole life costs to understand the balance between capital, life cycle and operations costs (Be, 2003). From inception to completion collaborative environment is keen in PPP/PFI arrangements. They offer an opportunity for consortia to form integrated teams from day one, allowing the project team to better understand the client end needs. Collaboration with the end users at the feasibility stage enable the SPV to establish the correct business case while the early involvement of the supply chain offers competitive advantages during the bid process. Another essential element is the quality of the design, early collaboration between designers, installers, operators and the supply chain affects the whole life cost. The design team should focus on delivery what is actually need instead of focusing in specifications to allow innovation, being the collaboration with end users, once again important. Design flexibility is also important since PPP/PFI have long-term relations, predictability of what may be need in the future can be a commercial opportunity, and

project team should collaborate with governments departments to understand what may be required and incorporate flexibility on the design to allow future changes (Be, 2003).

Integrated IT systems also play a key role in collaborative working in PPP/PFI arrangements. Extranets can provide a security access to all internal stakeholders to store and share documents in a single system avoiding duplication of administration and providing information on who access the information and when. In long-term contracts this technology allows operators of the facility to access relevant information such “as built” that can help in the maintenance of the asset at different stages of the project life cycle (Be, 2003).

According to Clifton and Duffield (2006) research generally in PPP/PFI arrangements there are many deficient contract relationships that can be solve by using alliance techniques. However, this technique did not gained wide industry acceptance. All the previous tools and techniques discussed in chapter one are being used in this particular procurement route. The shift of risk from the public client to the SPV seems to have a positive effect on embracing the tool and techniques to effective collaboration in these special arrangements.

3.4 PPP/PFI Project Life Cycle

In long term agreement of a PPP/PFI it is crucial to take in consideration the whole life cycle cost in order to establish the project budget. Since the private sector is responsible not just for the construction but also to operate the asset, not only the initial capital cost but also the running and operational costs should be considered (Wang, 2014). Life cycle cost can be an important tool to help on the selection of alternative projects, designs or building components and to forecast operations costs in the future, helping to assess the optimum competitive bid and at the same time ensure the delivery of the required service with quality (Swaffield and McDonald, 2008). Therefore, PPP/PFI have to go through a complex process to ensure that delivers value for money in comparison with alternative procurement routes.

Traditionally the process of PPP/PFI projects develop in eight stages, the project selection and definition, option assessment, getting organised, pre-tendering work, bidding process, contract and financial close, contract management, and ex-post evaluation, these stages can be incorporated into three interconnected phases: initiation

and planning, procurement, and partnership that compose the PPP/PFI project life cycle (Liu et al., 2015).

3.4.1 Initiation and planning

According to EIB (2012) guide this phase is divided into two distinct phases project identification (initiation) and detailed preparation (planning). In the first phase the objective is to ensure that the investment offers value for money and to assess the PPP/PFI option. The second is to organise the project and prepare for the tender. Liu et al. (2015) organised these phases in six principal heading:

1. Pre-project study;
2. Feasibility study;
3. Risk management;
4. Value for money analysis;
5. Project and advisory team organisation.
6. Design of PPP arrangement and pre-tendering preparation.

At this phase a transparent and effective assessment to ensure that this procurement route offers more value for money is required since the decision of following this procurement route depends on this criteria (EIB, 2012, Liu et al., 2015).

3.4.2 Procurement Phase

It is important to ensure a transparent and competitive procurement process to guarantee the project success. This phase starts with the publication of the procurement notice and ends with financial close. After this, the detailed design and construction can start. This phase was divided into two stages the first bidding process that has four tasks:

1. Procurement notice, prequalification and shortlisting;
2. Invitation to tender;
3. Interaction Pith bidders;
4. Evaluation of tenders and PPP contract award.
5. The second stage contract and financial close divided into three tasks:
6. Finalise PPP contract,
7. Conclude financing agreements,
8. Reach financial close (EIB, 2012, Liu et al., 2015).

The bidding process should be competitive, transparent and standardised otherwise the result may be time and cost overruns and inappropriate selection for concessioner. At contract and financial close both parties will reach the final agreement. The financial close enables the funds to start the project implementation. In order not to delay the project the public authorities should design, implement, and maintain an effective final negotiations framework and financial close procedures (Liu et al., 2015).

3.4.3 Partnership Phase

After the financial close the contract is awarded and the project enters in the partnership phase constituted by the following stages construction, operation and maintenance. This phase is a very important part of the PPP/PFI life cycle because the implementation of the project begins from this point. The contract must be implemented accordingly with the terms of the contract, effective contract management to correctly allocation of responsibilities, monitor the outputs, change management and dispute resolution is important at this phase otherwise the project will fail to meet stakeholders expectation (EIB, 2012, Liu et al., 2015). The construction phase in complex PPP/PFI projects can take a few years to complete effective management of cost, time and quality is expected to be carry out, also health and safety, resources utilisation, conflict and protuberant techniques/skills in construction are considered critical success factors for this phase (Liu et al., 2015, Wang, 2014).

Effective facilities management also play a key role at this phase, in some contract facilities management is carried out by different contractors or by different division of the same firm that built the asset. Consequently, a major focus on low capital cost in the construction phase can have a negative impact on the maintenance budget and implication on the profitability of the contract (Swaffield and McDonald, 2008). However, this issue has not been addressed in the process of many PPP/PFI contracts (Liu et al., 2015). In order to ensure the quality of the project evaluation is essential. Construction projects are subject to evaluation after completion, however, due to the nature of PPP/PFI arrangements the project should be evaluated at all phases of the project life cycle in order to ensure the optimum service quality of the asset (Liu et al., 2015).

3.5 BIM and PPP/PFI life cycle

The nature of the PPP/PFI arrangements where the SPV is responsible for building, maintain and operate an asset provides the perfect environment for the implementation of BIM. The SPV needs to establish a business case for the use of BIM to enable the advantages of this technology throughout the project life cycle (Love et al., 2015). In order to make the most out of BIM it is important that stakeholders are involved at an early stage during the initiation and planning phase of the project life cycle (Love et al., 2014, Azhar et al., 2012). This early involvement is important not just to ensure a design that is optimised for quality, aesthetics and affordability but also to enable the building information model to be loaded with important data throughout the whole process to provide essential information to effectively operate and maintain the asset (Azhar et al., 2012). BIM making use of formats such as Construction Operations Building Information Exchange (COBie) enables a more efficient and effective collection of information that can be incorporated during the operations and maintenance stages (Serginson and Lockley, 2012). Introducing the facility manager at an early stage of the project is important to provide essential information to be considered on the design stage and potentially increase value for money. BIM can help to collect and save essential data form the initial phase including equipment lists, product data sheets, warranties, spare parts lists, and preventive maintenance schedules that are crucial to support operations, maintenance and enable the effectively management of the asset (Love et al., 2015).

BIM enables collaborative work by providing a platform where information throughout the project life cycle can be shared by different stakeholder.

3.5.1 Initiation and Planning Phase

At this phase the emphasis is on the finance, taxation and legal issues associated with the business case for the PPP/PFI. BIM has tools and techniques that can be helpful for analysing these issues. Usually at this phase a BIM LOD 100 (*“Conceptual, overall building massing indicative of area, height, volume, location and orientation may be modeled in three dimensions or represented by other data”* (Yoders, 2012)) can be established to compare the costs using “5D cost planning” with similar assets helping to determine these issues. With this process inefficiencies and opportunities can be identified and pointed to improve the overall performance including the sustainability of

the asset and allow modifications and improvements to be made during the design and construction phase adding value to the project (Azhar et al., 2008, Azhar et al., 2012, Cheung et al., 2012, Love et al., 2015). 5D planning can help to review income and concessionaire elements of the project in different time periods, evaluate depreciation to determine taxation benefits helping to forecast consistent returns during the whole project (Love et al., 2015). The BIM LOD 100 also enable the external stakeholders to visualise how the project is going to merge with the landscape and existing facilities. For some assets space inventory can be made to determine areas for rooms, departments/functions and providing information on leasing options as part of finance helping to forecast revenues (Azhar et al., 2012, Love et al., 2015). It is also important that whole life cycle cost is taken in consideration since this information is crucial for the SPV to ensure the success of the project. Commissioning life cycle cost during this phase with 5D BIM can help to improve the design by considering cost information with regards to operation, all maintenance needed, residual values, and finance charges and when the design reaches the detailed design stage using advance 3D modelling the project costs can be more accurately calculated especial due to the ability of the stakeholders to visualise the entire context of the asset (Azhar et al., 2008, Azhar et al., 2012).

3.5.2 Procurement Phase

At this phase the design and construction process are addressed. According to Love et al. (2015) these processes have been the focus for the implementation of BIM and the advantages of implementing BIM through procurement phase are well known and include the following:

1. Improve design and its visualisation, it is possible to simulate the asset and the performance benchmarked;
2. Improve productivity information is more easily shared and coordinated;
3. Improve constructability, detailed analysis of sequence plan and operation can be simulated; and
4. Embedding quantity take offs and specifications of materials required for estimation and tendering (Azhar et al., 2008, Azhar et al., 2012, Love et al., 2015).

According to Merschbrock and Munkvold (2015) study, clients want to save money on operations, and BIM models can help to make decisions in facility management, and to actively include users in the design resulting in better facilities. Visualisation improve the end users commitment to the project since they better understand what will be constructed (Love et al., 2015). Design options such as green roofs, building orientation, sustainable material and energy modelling can be virtually tested to improve life cycle performance improving project profitability, and omissions and errors can be avoided by the quality of the design visualisation and the collaboration of the design stakeholders that by using the same platform can detect incompatibilities among the varied services specialities, a process called clash detection (Azhar and Brown, 2009, Love et al., 2015). This process not just reduces the conflicts during the construction stage but also reduce the change orders and reworks that can result in costs overruns. Also, using BIM makes it easy to check building regulations and ensure that what has been specified and installed is in compliance with the regulatory requirements (Azhar et al., 2008, Azhar et al., 2012, Love et al., 2015).

According to Oh et al. (2015) all the information produced at the design stage can be stored and manage in an integrated manner in a BIM server that in the future can be accessed by different stakeholders. This information is useful for monitoring planned work with what was actually constructed in real-time. Also the progress on site can be recorded via smart phone or tablet and loaded into the cloud or BIM server and stakeholders can have direct access to this information to monitor and improving the decision making (Ding and Xu, 2014, Love et al., 2015).

3.5.3 Partnership Phase

At this phase the asset is built, managed and operated during the arrangement period. Over the construction stage the building information modelling had suffered some changes and needs to be revised in order to validate the “as-Built”. At this stage the BIM is synchronised with the facility management system to enable important information such as data cost to be transferred between these systems and be used during the project life cycle allowing cost performance to be followed after the construction of the asset. Advantages of using BIM on early phases starts to appear, providing the facility operators with crucial data that allow effective management of the facility (Azhar et al., 2012, Love et al., 2015). Important information regarding to the location of equipment, model number, operations and maintenance manuals make the

facilities management more efficient (Azhar et al., 2012). According to Kassem et al. (2015) BIM can improve facilities management by improving the quality of the information and the handover process, also the 3D environment improves visualisation that allows to simulate a variety of scenarios plans for future refurbishment.

Also, the materials management process can be improved by introducing radio frequency identification tags and barcodes to monitor materials to permit a more efficient planning and ordering management process. This information is also important to provide the public sector with the information regarding the performance of the asset and guaranty that adequate maintenance is being carry out (Love et al., 2015).

3.5.4 Barriers for Implementation

BIM technology enables collaborative work and potentially improve work process throughout the life cycle of a PPP/PFI projects exist. However, there are some scholars that believe that collaborative work is not raised by BIM (Love et al., 2011). The reason may lay on barriers for implementation of BIM technology in the construction industry. According to Gu and London (2010) the lack of training, fragmentation of the industry and the reluctance to change the existing work practice are some of the causes. Also, the existing BIM applications are too specific targeting specific aspects of the project and there is a lack of supporting tools that enable integration of all aspects of the project. Oh et al. (2015) supports this idea with their analysis on the use of different software's. They found that there are major data losses when the model is used by different designers. This could be related to the nature of their work and the use of different software and tools. The high initial investment can also be an obstacle to corporate leaders making decisions on implementing this technology (Ding and Xu, 2014). Furthermore, many corporate leaders are sceptical about the business value offered by BIM technology since frequently companies fail to establish common infrastructures for BIM within and between organizations (Merschbrock and Munkvold, 2015).

Although BIM had been already exhaustively experimented in the project design stage and the benefits being well known, in other stages such as cost estimations, escalation of future expenditure and present value cost, discounts rates and study period data that is required for life cycle cost have not been widely used therefore, the whole life-cycle costs cannot be effectively generated (Love et al., 2015).

3.7 Conclusion

In order to review PPP/PFI contracts a literature review was carried out to appraise PPP/PFI contracts, review the project life cycle, investigate the advantages of BIM during the whole life cycle and the barriers for implementation of BIM in PPP/PFI projects. The review found that this particular procurement route promotes collaborative working and although there have been a few problems in some projects it is possible to deliver value for money to the taxpayers throughout these contracts. In order to achieve project success effective collaboration must start upstream on the project life cycle with internal stakeholders from design, construction, operations and maintenance collaborating to achieve the same goal, a project where the initial capital cost is well balance with future operations costs and deliveries value for money to the tax payers.

Three major phases on a PPP/PFI project life cycle were found, the initiation and planning, procurement and partnership. All these phases have to deal with issues related to operations and maintenance costs that are difficult to forecast. In the past limited tools and techniques have been limited to ensure accurate costs. However, with BIM technology is now possible to develop a virtual model of the asset where different scenarios can be simulated to forecast all these costs more accurately. Also, the virtual model can be loaded with important information throughout the project life cycle that can be stored in the company server or in a cloud system enabling different stakeholders to remotely access this vital information for decision making improving collaborative working. BIM technology can now help stakeholders to visualize the project before being constructed and to add value at each phase of the project life cycle.

Although BIM has shown that can bring many advantages on the entire process there are still some barriers that need to be addressed. Issues related to training, people reluctance to change, initial investment and reluctance from top management are some of the barriers that are obstructing the implementation of this technology. Also, there still are some issues related to interoperability of different applications causing loss of important data. These issues lead to the supposition that BIM may not be raising collaborative work in PPP/PFI projects. Although, this technology have proved the positive affect that can have throughout the project life cycle and on collaborative work a question on how much BIM can enhance collaborative work remains to be answered. The next chapter addresses the best methodology to exam this hypothesis.

Chapter Four: Research Methods

4.1 Introduction

In order to test the hypothesis, the aims and objectives needs to be evaluated through an application of research techniques. This particular chapter reviews various existing research techniques which allows to identify the best methodology to answer the established aim and objectives.

4.2 Research Methodology

There is no consensus on the definition of research strategy, and these results might lead to unreliable approaches that especially in the built environment have gather much criticism (Amaratunga et al., 2002). According to Naoum (2007) research strategy can be defined as “the way in which the research objectives can be questioned” and can be divided into two strategies namely “quantitative research” and “qualitative research”. These strategies diverge on the approach to data collection and analyses hence, their advantages and disadvantages and the research situation should be taken in consideration when deciding on which one to follow (Amaratunga et al., 2002).

According to Naoum (2007) quantitative research is objective and can be defined as an inquiry into social or human problem. The data collected is not abstract because numerical and statistical procedures are used to test the hypothesis. On the other hand, qualitative research is subjective and more appropriated for the description, meaning and experiences of people in real life. Furthermore, qualitative research can be divided in to two categories exploratory and attitudinal. The former is used when there is a lack of knowledge about the research topic, and is connected to the need to clear out the recognised problem whereas, attitudinal research is used to make subject evaluation of people behaviour about a particular issue (Naoum, 2007).

The two methods are appropriated for research in the built environment. Qualitative research is gauging acceptance in the built environment while quantitative due to the possibility of collecting extensive data with limit resources of time and budget is widely used especially in the academic environment (Amaratunga et al., 2002).. Table 1 shows a summary of advantages and disadvantages of these two methods adopted from (Amaratunga et al., 2002, Naoum, 2007).

Table 1 - Advantages and disadvantages of qualitative and quantitative research.

Method	Advantages	Disadvantages
Quantitative	<p>Can cover a wide range of scenarios;</p> <p>Its efficient, fast and cost effective with comprehensive statistics collected from substantial samples which are relevant to policy decisions;</p> <p>Provides hard and reliable data;</p> <p>Keep a distance between the researchers and the subject.</p>	<p>The system is artificial and obstinate;</p> <p>They are not effectual in apprehending processes or in distinguishing the significance people fasten to their actions;</p> <p>It does not promote theory generation;</p> <p>Focus on aspects such as ‘what is’ or ‘what has’ which makes it strenuous for policy makers to deduce ‘what changes’ and derive future actions.</p>
Qualitative	<p>The data collection is more organic than artificial;</p> <p>It provides the potential to change processes overtime;</p> <p>It helps in understanding peoples meaning;</p> <p>Provides the capacity to adapt with emerging issues and ideas;</p> <p>Promotes theory generation;</p> <p>Provides rich and deep data.</p>	<p>The process of data collection is wearisome and requires additional resources;</p> <p>Data analysis and understanding is difficult;</p> <p>The control of research process, pace, and progress is hard;</p> <p>The results of qualitative approach is given low credibility by the policy makers.</p>

According to Bryman (2006) these two methods can be mixed to help researchers to elucidate the nature of their intentions or of their accomplishments. Creswell (2003) recognised the limitations of both methods and states that biases found in any method can be overrun by mixing with biases of other methods. Therefore, these two methods can be used to complement each other.

After consideration of both available methods a quantitative approach was selected to carry out the research as it provided an opportunity to gather objective data that is valuable in terms collecting a set of quantifiable facts that could be used to assess the impact of BIM on collaborative work on PPP/PFI projects by statistical analysis. The appropriateness of qualitative data was regarded as being inadequate in terms of addressing the specific aims and objectives of the research as outlined.

4.3 Research Design

According to Naoum (2007) research hypotheses should be formulated in one-sentence that clearly and specifically states what needs to be investigated and can be defined as tentative proposition that through investigation is expose to verification. In accordance to chapter one, the hypothesis to be tested is the collaboration between internal stakeholders during the whole life cycle of the PPP/PFI agreement will be enhanced due to the introduction of BIM?

This hypothesis is appropriate to test the aim and objectives of the dissertation and is been examined on the research. The dissertation has employed two types of research methods:

1. Secondary, desk study.
2. Primary, field work.

In order to gauge information to better understand the subject and to find gaps for further research, a desk study was conducted by an extensive and comprehensive literature review from construction research journals and articles, construction magazines, governments reports, university journals and articles and online sources. The desk study has answered some questions, however, due to the multitude of variables of the topic some gaps that need be addressed were raised and for this reason a field study became essential.

According to (Naoum, 2007) when quantitative methods are selected a series of hypothesis and sub-hypothesis should be put in a theoretical framework to be tested. Therefore, a number of sub-hypothesis to examine these gaps are going to be investigated to allow the evaluation of BIM as a collaborative working agent in a PPP/PFI project. The following sub-hypothesis will be investigated:

1. To find out whether communications are enhanced in a PPP/PFI project that used BIM;
2. To investigate the effects BIM has on people behaviour;
3. To compare the information flow through project life cycle in a PPP/PFI project with and without the use of BIM;
4. To investigate the barriers that are lagging a wider usage of BIM.

4.4 Data Collection

According to Naoum (2007) there is two major techniques to collect data postal questionnaire and personal interview. The former has been widely used primarily due to economical and speed advantages on collecting analytical surveys on people perceptions, views and opinions. The latter technique is also suitable to collect factual information and opinions. However, due to the requirement of face to face relationship makes it slower to collect data from a large pool of participants is needed (Naoum, 2007).

Since the researcher has the objective of collecting as much data as possible in a short period of time the postal questionnaire presents the best method to collect these data. For this reason the postal questionnaire was selected for data collection.

4.5 Survey Questionnaire

As mentioned above the literature review as uncovered some doubts on how effective BIM is to enhance collaborative work in PPP/PFI projects. For this reason the following set of sub-hypothesis need to be investigated:

1. To find out whether communications are enhanced in a PPP/PFI project that used BIM;
2. To investigate the effects BIM has on people behaviour;
3. To compare the information flow through project life cycle in a PPP/PFI project with and without the use of BIM;
4. To investigate the barriers that are lagging a wider usage of BIM.

A postal questionnaire was design do investigate each one of these sub-hypothesis. It is composed of ten questions and can be divided in six sections as follows:

Section 1 (Qn. 1 to 4) – This section initiates the questionnaire and has de objective of collecting information regarding to the background of the respondent and the type of organisation.

Section 2 (Qn. 5) – The objective of this question is to select the right “specimen” from a randomly sample. The question has a logical feature that allow participants with experience in PPP/PFI projects that used BIM to proceed with the questionnaire and

provide the relevant information to fulfil the objectives of the research while the one without this specific experience will receive the information that the questionnaire is over.

Section 3 (Qn. 6 and 7) – This section has the objective of investigating whether communications are enhanced in a PPP/PFI project that used BIM the first sub-hypothesis of the research. Knowledge acquired in chapter two where BIM was study in a technology strategy that can improve communications were link to chapter three by introducing it in a specific PPP/PFI project. The literature review indicated that BIM can improve communication this section is going to test this hypothesis.

Section 4 (Qn. 6 and 8) – The questions on section four investigate the effects BIM has on people behaviour (the second sub-hypothesis). This question is related to people's strategy review in chapter two and linked to PPP/PFI projects in chapter three. This strategy as seen in chapter three as becoming an important key factor for construction project success with trust playing a very important role in PPP/PFI projects.

Section 5 (Qn. 6 and 9) – This section is going to investigate the third sub-hypothesis of the research that is to compare the information flow through project life cycle in a PPP/PFI project with and without the use of BIM. This objective is mostly link to the third chapter but there are some issues that are also linked to the business strategy appraised in chapter two to the specific early involvement of supply chain.

Section 6 (Qn. 10) – This question is going to investigate the barriers that are lagging a wider usage of BIM and are related to the last sub-hypothesis. In chapter two and three the literature review found out some of the barrier to collaborative work and the introduction of BIM in the industry.

4.6 Pilot Study

Naoum (2007) advises researches to conduct a pilot study always before the final submission of the questionnaires to the whole sample. This is particularly important since the trial can provide significant information on the wording, question formulation, mistakes and ambiguous or unclear questions. Also, it can provide valuable information on the time needed to finish the survey, whether the instructions are clear and if the layout of the questionnaire is clear and captures the responder attention to motivate the survey completion (Naoum, 2007).

Subsequently, a pilot test was conducted and the feedback helped to refine the layout. An online survey account was used to distribute the survey via email to construction companies across UK. The pilot study showed that the survey takes less than ten minutes to complete.

4.7 Research Sample

Now that the questionnaire and the pilot study are done a decision on the characteristics of the participants needs to be taken. According to Naoum (2007) this process is very important and should be carefully treated otherwise the target participants may not be categorised the scope of the research. The research is trying to evaluate how effective BIM is to promote collaborative work in PPP/PFI projects for this reason the survey should target professionals involved in projects procured through PPP/PFI contracts and at the same time are using BIM.

Subsequently, a representative sample of these professionals needs to be surveyed. Naoum (2007) claimed that a representative sample can be established by two different ways “random” and “non-random”. The former is appropriated for collecting large number of data, however, the sampling not always has the specific characteristics of the entire population and it just can be used when these characteristics are not critical. The latter is suitable for interview where participants with specific characteristics are interviewed (Naoum, 2007).

The questionnaire survey was randomly distributed across companies in the construction sector of the United Kingdom. However, the questionnaire has a specific question that automatically selected the target population. The questionnaire was sent to 100 companies through online survey. Despite the number of reminders sent every three days following the two weeks the survey was available just 29 responses were collected. However, three questionnaires returned incomplete and just 12 participants were representative of the population intended to be surveyed and can be used in this research. Although, the level of responses not being the ideal, time limitation did not allow to wait for more responses.

4.8 Data Analysis

The data collected by the questionnaire survey will have a statistic treatment and will be presented in the form of pie charts, diagrams and tables. A brief review of the findings will be followed by a discussion on the results.

A Likert scale of 1 to 5, where 1 represents “Not at all enhanced”, 2 “Slightly enhanced”, 3 “Somewhat enhanced”, 4 “Very enhanced” and 5 “Extremely enhanced” is going to be used to gauge the perception of the professionals. An average rating is going to be calculated and classified as follow (Kostoulas, 2013):

Table 2 - Likert Scale Classification

Average Rating	Classification
$1 \leq \text{average rating} \leq 1.5$	Not at all enhanced
$1.5 \leq \text{average rating} \leq 2.5$	Slightly enhanced
$2.5 \leq \text{average rating} \leq 3.5$	Somewhat enhanced
$3.5 \leq \text{average rating} \leq 4.5$	Very enhanced
$4.5 \leq \text{average rating} \leq 5$	Extremely enhanced

4.8 Conclusion

This chapter reviewed the existing research techniques that best address the aims and objectives of this dissertation, and the quantitative method was selected to test the research hypothesis. To collect the data a postal questionnaire with ten questions were sent through Survey Monkey. A pilot test helped to improve the questionnaire and show that the survey can be completed in less than ten minutes. The survey intended to evaluate BIM as an enabler of collaborative work in PPP/PFI projects hence; professionals that used BIM in these projects were target. The following chapter will review the responses of the survey and provide analysis of the data collected.

Chapter Five: Data Collection and Analysis

5.1 Introduction

The aim of this chapter is to review and discuss the results of the questionnaire survey.

5.2 Response Review

The objective of this survey was to evaluate BIM as a collaborative working agent in a PPP/PFI project. The questionnaire was developed in six sections that address different sub-hypothesis. Below follows an overview of the responses of each section.

5.2.1 Section one – General Information

This section is composed of four questions. It starts by asking to the participants their job description. The responses collected show that the survey reached a variety of professionals with three Architects representing 25% of the respondents following by two Project Managers, Design Engineers, and Consultants representing around 17% each. In addition, three more professionals Project Director, Site Engineer and BIM Manager representing about 8% each. The chart below displays the proportion of whole professionals.

Figure 1 - Job Designation.

The second question addressed the years of experience the participants have in the construction industry. The results in figure 2 show that most of the participants have a vast experience in the industry with half the respondents having more than 20 years of experience (1 Project Director, Project Manager, 2 Architects, Consultant and a Design Engineer) and one quarter between 10 and 15 years of experience (1 Project Manager, Site Manager and 1 Architect). The remaining quarter have less experience between 5 and 10 years (Consultant, Design Engineer and a BIM Manager).

Figure 2 - Proportion of Work Experience.

The third question was related to the type of organisation the participants represents. This question also shows a variety of business as seen in figure 3. Consultancy companies in summary are represented by five professionals corresponding to around 41% of the respondents, two of them Structural Consultants (approximately 16%), and one of each, BIM Consultant, Project Management Consultant and Building Consultant representing around 8% individually. Architects are almost 17% (2 people), Contractors and Subcontractors also represent around 17% each (2 people each). Last an Infrastructure Project Manager that did not specify to represent a consultancy or a subcontractor at around 8%. Unfortunately, Clients and Facility Managers are not represented.

Figure 3 - Type of Organization.

The fourth question is related to the phase of the project these professionals have been involved in. The data in figure 4 shows that the majority of professionals are involved in the Design and Specifications phase representing more than 83% (10 out of 12), following by Feasibility and Studies, and Planning and Construction representing around 58% (7 out of 12) and 50% (6 out of 12) respectively. The last is represented by two Main Contractors and four Subcontractors. Bidding and Negotiations follows with more than 33% (4 out of 12) and Facility Management with around 8% (1 out of 12). Two respondents selected Construction Supervision and a Witness on Construction Disputes both are related to construction phase and represent almost 17% (2 out of 12).

Figure 4 - Phase of the Project Life Cycle the professionals have been Involved.

5.2.2 Section two – Selecting the Sampling

The objective of this section is to select the right professionals to continue the survey. All the participants being analysed have answer yes to this question.

5.2.3 Section Three – Improvements BIM brings to Communications in PPP/PFI projects

The objective of this section is to find out if BIM improves communications in a PPP/PFI project. Making use of the Likert scale an average score of the responses of the first question was calculated. The overall average on communication score was 3.00 out of 5 (Somewhat enhanced) and the professionals that gave better scores were related to the design stage with the exception of one architect. The results indicate a positive effect of BIM on communications. As shown in table 3 manage project data and information score the higher mark with 3.50 (Very enhanced) while security of confidential information the lowest with 2.17 (Slightly enhanced).

Table 3 - Improvements of BIM in Communications.

Answer Options	Rating Average	Classification
Manage project data and information.	3.50	Somewhat enhanced
Access to project data and information.	3.33	Somewhat enhanced
Share project data and information.	3.25	Somewhat enhanced
Openness to information sharing.	3.00	Somewhat enhanced
Credibility of the information shared.	2.92	Somewhat enhanced
Quality of information.	2.83	Somewhat enhanced
Security of confidential information.	2.17	Slightly enhanced
Total Average:		3.00
		Somewhat enhanced

Figure 5 illustrates the proportion of answers on the seven communication factors.

Figure 5 - Proportion of answers on the seven communication factors.

When the participants were asked whether BIM can improve communication between stakeholders 42% have answered “Somewhat improved”, 33% “Very improved” and 25% “Slightly improved” scoring an average rate of 3.08 (Somewhat improved) in line with the previous questions (figure 6).

Figure 6 - BIM as an Enabler of Communication Answers Distribution.

5.2.4 Section Four – Improvements BIM brings to People Behaviours in PPP/PFI projects

This section aims to investigate the effect BIM has on people’s behaviour. In table 4 the factors related to people’s behaviour scored an overall average of 2.60 (Slightly enhance) being the higher average score team work with 3.17 (Somewhat enhanced) and the smaller tensions reduction with 2.17 (Slightly enhance). Disputes resolution 3.00 (Somewhat enhanced) and work environment 2.50 (Somewhat enhanced). The answers appears not to have any connection to work experience or job designation of the participants.

Table 4 - Improvements of BIM in Communications.

Answer Options	Rating Average	Classification
Team work.	3.17	Somewhat enhanced
Disputes resolution.	3.00	Somewhat enhanced
Share the decision making process.	2.67	Somewhat enhanced
Trust, respect and cooperation among stakeholders.	2.58	Somewhat enhanced
Work environment.	2.50	Slightly enhanced
Inter-disciplinary learning and skill transfer.	2.42	Slightly enhanced
Incentive to work.	2.25	Slightly enhanced
Reduce tensions.	2.17	Slightly enhanced
Total Average:	2.60	Somewhat enhanced

Figure 7 illustrates the proportion of answers on the eight behaviours factors.

Figure 7- Proportion of answers on behaviour factors.

The last question of this section was to investigate whether BIM can reduce conflicts. The majority of the participants (around 83%) supported the concept of conflict reduction with the application of BIM (figure 8). This question appears to contradict the previous question especially with regards to the low score of work environment and reduce tensions.

Figure 8 - Conflict Reduction by BIM.

5.2.5 Section five – Improvements BIM on the Flow of information through PPP/PFI projects

The objective of this section is to investigate whether the flow of information through the project life cycle is improved. Table 5 shows the overall score of this factor was 2.90 (Somewhat enhanced). The highest score coordination, synchronisation and sequence of the project with 3.50 (Somewhat enhanced) and the smallest score early involvement of supply chain with 2.50 (Slightly enhanced).

Table 5 - Improvements of BIM on the Flow of Information.

Answer Options	Rating Average	Classification
Co-ordination, synchronization and sequence of the project.	3.50	Somewhat enhanced
Flow of information through the project life cycle.	2.92	Somewhat enhanced
Discontinuity of information through project life cycle.	2.67	Somewhat enhanced
Early involvement of supply chain.	2.50	Slightly enhanced
Total Average:	2.90	Somewhat enhanced

Figure 9 illustrates the proportion of answers for the factors related to flow of information.

Figure 9- Proportion of answers on flow of information.

The second question of this section was intended to evaluate if BIM can encourage the early involvement of stakeholder. The great majority of the respondents (91.7%) believe that BIM can encourage this early involvement. Once again these questions appear to contradict the pervious question where the early involvement of the supply chain scored the lowest rating average (figure 10).

Figure 10 - BIM encouraging early involvement of stakeholders.

5.2.6 Section six – Barriers lagging a wider usage of BIM

The participants were asked to rank a set of barriers and in first place the initial investment was selected with a score of 4.42 followed by top management support (4.08), industry reluctance to change (3.92), reluctance from people towards technology (3.92), interoperability of BIM software's (2.83) and the last was lack of training (2.5). This result suggests that changes in the industry like accommodating a specific budget on public projects to introduce BIM can tackle the initial investment and help to change top management perspective (table 7).

Table 6- Rank of the barriers lagging the implementation of BIM.

Answer Options	1	2	3	4	5	6	Response Count	Score	Rank
Initial Investment.	25.00%	25.00%	33.33%	8.33%	0.00%	8.33%	12	4.42	1
Top management support.	25.00%	25.00%	16.67%	16.67%	0.00%	16.67%	12	4.08	2
Industry reluctance to change.	25.00%	33.33%	0.00%	8.33%	16.67%	16.67%	12	3.92	3
Reluctance from people toward technology.	8.33%	8.33%	33.33%	16.67%	16.67%	16.67%	12	3.25	4
Interoperability of BIM software's.	16.67%	8.33%	8.33%	0.00%	41.67%	25.00%	12	2.83	5
Lack of training.	0.00%	0.00%	8.33%	50.00%	25.00%	16.67%	12	2.5	6

5.3 Findings and Discussions of Responses

The aim of the questionnaire survey was to collect data from stakeholders that are involved in PPP/PFI projects that use BIM. This research is evaluating BIM as a collaborative working agent in these type of projects and to what extent this technology improves collaborative work. The first section of the survey collected data regarding to general information of the participants. As shown in the responses review, the survey reached a large variety, of mostly, experienced professionals that represent multi-disciplinary companies and are involved in different stages of these projects. Although, the number of returned questionnaires was not ideal, the vast number of experienced professionals and organisations covered most of the life cycle phases of the project and provided significant results for valid conclusions.

The third section of the questionnaire addressed the first sub-hypothesis of the research to find whether communications are enhanced by BIM in PPP/PFI projects. The first chapter showed how important communications are for effective collaborative working (Shelbourn et al., 2012). Communications also play an important role in PPP/PFI projects due to the vast number of stakeholders involved and the time frame of the contract agreement. However, the results indicate that communication in PPP/PFI projects do not change much with the use of BIM but still have a positive effect. The overall average of responses to factors related to communication range between 2.17 and 3.50 the final average was 3.00. Information management plays a very important role in these projects (Be, 2003, Love et al., 2015) and the participants have given the best mark 3.50, around 67% of the respondents feels that this process is “very enhanced” by BIM. Followed by access and share to project data and information scoring 3.33 and 3.25, respectively. The lowest score was security of confidential information with 2.17. This factor is very important in all types of contracts but in PPP/PFI where the SPV delivers a service and is responsible for the development of the entire project, the security of the information is taken even more seriously (Be, 2003). Improvements and easy access to information needs to be balanced with security. The most surprised score was 2.83 on quality of information. According to chapters two and three BIM enables designers to produce 3D project where the 3D objects are loaded with relevant information (Azhar et al., 2012, Love et al., 2015, Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010). The quality of information is particularly important for PPP/PFI to enable effective facility management (Ding and Xu, 2014, Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves,

2010). Half the professionals had a divided perception on the quality of information, 25% of the respondents answered “Slightly enhanced” and the other 25% feels that the quality is “Very enhanced”, the remaining professionals are distributed around 42% “Somewhat enhanced” and over 8% “Not at all enhanced”. Also surprising is the professionals that gave these answers. Most of the professionals involved at the design stage either feel that the quality is not at all, slightly or somewhat enhanced, with the exception of one architect and a project director that are involved in the design stage. The last question of this section asked the participants if communication among the stakeholders were improved by BIM. The overall response score 3.08 having a slightly improvement regarding to the first question. The perception of 33% of the professionals is that BIM “very improved” communication among stakeholders, 42% somewhat “improved” and the last 25% “Slightly improved”. Generally the results on the perception of the professionals surveyed regarding the improvements of BIM in communication in PPP/PFI projects were positive.

The fourth section of the questionnaire addresses the second sub-hypothesis of the research, to investigate the effects BIM has on people behaviour. As discussed in the second chapter behaviours such as trust and concern for relationship are very important for effective collaborative work (Xue et al., 2010). Hard negotiation during the contract of a PPP/PFI often result in conflicts and tension among stakeholders. Trust is essential to reduce these tensions and conflicts and is a key success factor on the delivery of these projects (Smyth and Edkins, 2007). The first question of this section addresses the improvements that BIM can bring to these behaviours. The overall average of responses to these factors was 2.60 with responses ranging between 2.17 and 3.17. Although, these scores still fall in the positive percentile the result shows that BIM do not have great impact on behaviour. The highest score was 3.17 on team work, this factor is very important in construction projects (Shelbourn and Bouchlaghem, 2012) and particular in these types of contracts, the result show that BIM can enable team work and subsequent improvements on time and cost. Trust, respect and cooperation among stakeholders scored 2.58. Despite the fact of BIM providing a platform where all stakeholders can open share and access information (Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010) the result shows little improvement on these factors. Some contradiction was found in two factors. Dispute resolution and reduce tension scoring 3.00 and 2.17, respectively. Although the participants felt that BIM has a positive effect on dealing with disputes it does not

reduce tension. Furthermore, when the participants were asked whether BIM can reduce conflicts in the second question of this section more than 83% of the responses were positive showing that these behaviours may not have any relationship. To address this contradiction a closer look to the responses given by a senior expert witness on construction disputes were considered. This participant score all these factor with 4.00 “Very enhanced”. Leaving this issue open for further discussion.

The fifth section of the survey investigates the third sub-hypothesis of the research, compare the flow of information through the PPP/PFI project life cycle with and without the use of BIM. Flow of information through PPP/PFI projects is important in order to deliver value for money to taxpayers (Baddeley and Chang, 2015, Ding and Xu, 2014). Chapter three shows that BIM provides facilities managers to access information related to the construction process enabling effective facilities management (Azhar et al., 2012, Grilo and Jardim-Goncalves, 2010). Early involvement of the supply chain can help to improve business case and innovation. The overall score of the first question was 2.90 showing that BIM somewhat can improve the flow of information. Coordination, synchronisation and sequence of the project score the highest average with 3.50 followed by flow of information through the project life cycle and discontinuity of information through project life cycle with 2.92 and 2.67, respectively. Early involvement of supply chain had the lowest score with 2.50 contradicting the next question of this section where more than 92% of the participants agreed that BIM could encourage early involvement of stakeholders in the project. Overall the perception of participants was positive showing that BIM brings some improvements to the flow of information and coordination of the project resulting in gains in time and cost.

The last section of the survey intended to discuss the last sub-hypothesis of the research, investigate the barriers that are lagging a wider usage of BIM. Barriers to implementation of BIM were described in chapter three. The last question asked the participants to rank the barrier that on their perception are causing the most impediments. The results suggest that there is a relationship in the top three barriers. In first place the participants selected initial Investment followed by top management support and in third place industry reluctance to change. The results indicate that changes in the industry are required to introduce BIM. Starting with clients where in order deal with the first two barriers should allocate a budget in the project partial cover the costs of BIM and with it stimulate the support of top management and cover the

initial investment. The public sector has one of the most important clients of construction services is already playing its part by approving legislation on mandatory BIM level two. The private sector should follow similar steps and with it improve the quality of their own asset.

5.4 Summary

This chapter reviewed and discussed the results of the questionnaire survey. From chapter two and three BIM show to be a technology that can bring great improvements to construction projects. However, the results of the survey are below what was expected. Supporting the idea that effective collaborative work should be seen in a more holistic perspective. Although, BIM as a technology can be an enabler of collaborative work other factor such as people and business are required to accomplish effective collaborative work.

Chapter Six: Conclusion and Recommendations

6.1 Introduction

The aim of this research was to evaluate BIM as an enabler of collaborative work in a PPP/PFI project. To pursue this research aim a set of aligned objectives were established and evaluation on how the research accomplished these objectives are presented. This chapter presents findings and limitation, followed by recommendations for future research.

6.2 Summary of the Research

The aim of this research was to evaluate how BIM can improve collaborative working during the whole life cycle of a PPP/PFI contract. To address this aim the following research objectives were established and investigated.

1. To critically apprise collaborative working in construction;
2. To review whole life cycle of a project delivered by PPP/PFI contract and advantages introduced by BIM;
3. To evaluate BIM as a collaborative working enabler;
4. To provide recommendations to support the implementation of BIM.

This objectives were investigated through this research and the accomplishments are presented below.

Objective 1: To critically apprise collaborative working in construction.

The literature review on collaborative working in chapter two revealed that to enable collaborative work three key strategies need to be aligned, business strategy, technology strategy and people strategy. The review identified that the industry is undertaking vast changes in these key strategies. The construction business have change and companies in order to become more competitive are partnering and making alliances. Governments are not different and are partnering with the private sector to deliver construction projects under PPP/PFI contracts that incorporate the whole life cycle of the project. This specific procurement route increases the pressure on collaborative work due the magnitude of stakeholders involved in these projects. Technology has evolved and improved communications for stakeholders to access, store and share information. BIM

is promising to revolutionise the industry, improving visualisation of projects in early phases and simulating whole life cycle of projects. The research revealed, increase interest among researchers, people's attitude and efforts among companies to stablish effective team work.

The literature review concluded that the barriers for effective collaborative work are related to people and organisation management.

Objective 2: To review whole life cycle of a project delivered by PPP/PFI contract and advantages introduced by BIM.

The literature review on PPP/PFI projects in chapter three identified three major phases of the project life cycle, planning, procurement, and partnership. At all stages stakeholders have to deal with issues related to operations and maintenance costs that are difficult to forecast. The research revealed that BIM could help stakeholders to visualise the project before being constructed and simulate different scenarios whilst giving an accurate cost forecast. Therefore, adding more value to each phase of the project life cycle. The research reveals that achieving effective project success through collaborative work must start upstream in the project life cycle and BIM is an efficient technology to enable it. Although, BIM proved to carry many advantages in PPP/PFI project life cycle, the research also exposed barriers that are hindering the implementation of BIM. Issues related to training, people reluctance to change, initial investment and reluctance of top management are some of the barriers that need to be addressed to promote the use of this technology.

The literature review concludes that BIM has a positive effect through PPP/PFI project life cycle and on collaborative work. However, question on how much BIM can enable collaborative work remains to be clarified. For this reason this question was chosen as the main focus of this research.

Objective 3: To evaluate BIM as a collaborative working enabler in PPP/PFI projects.

To evaluate BIM as a collaborative working enabler in PPP/PFI projects, an industry survey was carried out. Based on the results and gaps of the literature review, quantitative questionnaire was distributed among professionals in the UK construction industry. A set of sub-hypothesis were put in place and investigated through the survey. The results of the survey are presented in chapter five. The results, although below expectations showed a positive overall perception of BIM as an enabler of collaborative

work. Communications gauged the best perception followed by the flow of information through project life cycle whilst behavioural factors, still positive gauged the lowest perception.

The survey revealed that BIM could enable collaborative work. The participants quantified these improvements with 3 points out of 5. With this result, the research concludes that although collaborative work can be improved through the introduction of BIM effective collaborative work is only reached with the alignment of the three strategies.

Objective 4: To provide recommendations to support the implementation of BIM.

The literature review in chapter three revealed some of the barriers that are hindering the implementation of BIM in the construction industry. In the survey questionnaire the last sub-hypothesis investigated those barriers. The results in chapter five indicated that the three top barriers, initial investment, top management support and industry reluctance to change are related and if well addressed can help to support the implementation of BIM across the industry.

Chapter six concludes the research and provides recommendations to support the implementation of BIM.

6.3 Conclusion and Recommendations

This research evaluated how BIM can improve collaborative working during the whole life cycle of a PPP/PFI contract. BIM can improve many processes through the project life cycle and enhance collaborative work. However, to reach effective collaborative work, attention to all strategies, people, business and technology must be made. The early involvement of the supply chain must be addressed whilst people strategy have shown to have crucial behavioural traits such as trust and tensions that can be addressed to improve relationships and promote effective collaborative work.

This research concludes that to take fully advantage of BIM there are three major barriers that must be overcome; initial investment, top management support and industry reluctance. In order to address these issues clients must incorporate a budget in the projects and promote its implementation and by doing so the initial investment can be covered leading the industry, as a whole, and top level management's attitude to

change towards BIM and see the benefits, in terms of collaboration, that it has the potential to deliver.

6.4 Research Limitations

The research found several limitations. Firstly, a limited number of PPP/PFI projects delivered with the use of BIM at all stages of the project life cycle. PPP/PFI agreements can last for more than 40 years. BIM is a new technology and has mostly been used and tested only in the design stage as there is a lack of data suggesting its usage in other stages. Secondly, the survey did not reach out to any representatives of the clients and facilities managers that could have given vital feedback. Lastly, the number of responses collected was not ideal, the reason being lack of outreach to industry practitioners with experience in PPP/PFI delivered with the use of BIM and also limitation of time to conduct the survey.

6.5 Recommendations for Further Research

The presented study illustrates the complexity of an effective collaborative working environment and PPP/PFI projects. This particular procurement route incorporates the whole life cycle of projects, allowing researchers of the built environment to test any theory that can bring improvements to the industry. During this study the following areas for further research were identified:

1. Development of a framework for implementation of BIM in the whole life cycle of a PPP/PFI project.
2. Solutions to implement early involvement of supply chain.
3. Solution to improve security of confidential information in a BIM communication platform.

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Appendix A: Survey Cover Letter

Subject: Dissertation-MSc Construction Project Management / Questionnaire Survey Request.

Dear Sir/Madam,

I am currently undertaking a Master of Science Degree in Construction Project Management at Heriot-Watt University in Edinburgh. In fulfilment of this Dissertation I am required to research a topic area and produce a dissertation. The topic I have chosen is “How BIM can improve collaborative work during the Whole-Life-Cycle of a project delivered through PPP/PFI arrangement” and I am investigating the following aspects of its use:

- To find out whether communications are enhanced in a PPP/PFI project that used BIM;
- To investigate the effects BIM has on people behaviour;
- To compare the information flow through project life cycle in a PPP/PFI project with and without the using BIM;
- To investigate the barriers that are lagging a wider usage of BIM.

I would be very grateful if you could complete the below questionnaire link this will not take more than 10 minutes of your time. Needless to say the information provided will be treated with strict confidence and individual firms will not be identified.

Thanking you in advance,

Sincerely,

Miguel Moreira

Appendix B: Questionnaire Survey

BIM as a Collaborative Working Agent in a PPP/PFI Project

1. Please specify your job designation?

- Project Director
- Project Manager
- Site Manager
- Architect
- Consultant
- Design Engineer
- Quantity Surveyor
- Project Engineer
- Facilities Manager

Other (please specify)

2. Please specify the years of experience you have in the construction industry?

- 1 to 5
- 5 to 10
- 10 to 15
- 15 to 20
- Above 20

3. Please indicate the type of organization you are present employed with?

- Client
- Project Management Consultant
- Contractor
- Subcontractor
- Structural Consultant
- Mechanical and Electrical Consultant
- Facilities Management
- Other (please specify)

4. Please indicate the phase of the project where you have been involved in?

- Feasibility & Studies
- Design & Specification
- Bidding & Negotiation
- Planning & Construction as Main Contractor
- Planning & Construction as Subcontractor
- Facilities Management

Other (please specify)

5. Have you ever been involved in a project delivered by PPP/PFI procurement route that at any stage utilized BIM?

- Yes
- No

BIM as a Collaborative Working Agent in a PPP/PFI Project

6. From your experience to what extent did BIM enhance the following compared to a PPP/PFI project that did not used BIM?

	Not at all enhanced	Slightly enhanced	Somewhat enhanced	Very enhanced	Extremely enhanced
Access to project data and information.	<input type="radio"/>				
Share project data and information.	<input type="radio"/>				
Manage project data and information.	<input type="radio"/>				
Openness to information sharing.	<input type="radio"/>				
Quality of information.	<input type="radio"/>				
Security of confidential information.	<input type="radio"/>				
Credibility of the information shared.	<input type="radio"/>				
Trust, respect and cooperation among stakeholders.	<input type="radio"/>				
Share the decision making process.	<input type="radio"/>				
Team work.	<input type="radio"/>				
Incentive to work.	<input type="radio"/>				
Inter-disciplinary learning and skill transfer.	<input type="radio"/>				
Work environment.	<input type="radio"/>				
Reduce tensions.	<input type="radio"/>				
Disputes resolution.	<input type="radio"/>				
Discontinuity of information through project life cycle.	<input type="radio"/>				
Flow of information through the project life cycle.	<input type="radio"/>				
Early involvement of supply chain.	<input type="radio"/>				
Co-ordination, synchronization and sequence of the project.	<input type="radio"/>				

7. From your experience to what extent did BIM improve communications among different stakeholders at different stages of the PPP/PFI project life cycle?

Not at all improved	Slightly improved	Somewhat improved	Very improved	Extremely improved
<input type="radio"/>				

8. From your experience did BIM reduce the number of conflicts at the stage of the PPP/PFI project you have been involved with?

- Yes
- No

9. Do you believe that BIM can encourage early involvement of stakeholders that just has stake at a later stage in order to improve project performance?

- Yes
- No

10. Based on your experience please rank the following barriers to BIM implementation:

<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Lack of training.
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Industry reluctance to change.
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Initial Investment.
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Top management support.
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Reluctance from people toward technology.
<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	Interoperability of BIM software's.

Appendix C: Survey Results

Q1 Please specify your job designation?

Answered: 11 Skipped: 1

Answer Choices	Responses	
Project Director	9.09%	1
Project Manager	18.18%	2
Site Manager	9.09%	1
Architect	27.27%	3
Consultant	18.18%	2
Design Engineer	18.18%	2
Quantity Surveyor	0.00%	0
Project Engineer	0.00%	0
Facilities Manager	0.00%	0
Total		11

Q2 Please specify the years of experience you have in the construction industry?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
1 to 5	0.00% 0
5 to 10	25.00% 3
10 to 15	25.00% 3
15 to 20	0.00% 0
Above 20	50.00% 6
Total	12

Q3 Please indicate the type of organization you are present employed with?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
Client	0.00% 0
Project Management Consultant	8.33% 1
Contractor	16.67% 2
Subcontractor	16.67% 2
Structural Consultant	16.67% 2
Mechanical and Electrical Consultant	0.00% 0
Facilities Management	0.00% 0
Other (please specify)	41.67% 5
Total	12

Q4 Please indicate the phase of the project where you have been involved in?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
Feasibility & Studies	58.33% 7
Design & Specification	83.33% 10
Bidding & Negotiation	33.33% 4
Planning & Construction as Main Contractor	16.67% 2
Planning & Construction as Subcontractor	33.33% 4
Facilities Management	8.33% 1
Total Respondents: 12	

Q5 Have you ever been involved in a project delivered by PPP/PFI procurement route that at any stage utilized BIM?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses
Yes	100.00% 12
No	0.00% 0
Total	12

Q6 From your experience to what extent did BIM enhance the following compared to a PPP/PFI project that did not used BIM?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

	Not at all enhanced	Slightly enhanced	Somewhat enhanced	Very enhanced	Extremely enhanced	Total	Weighted Average
Access to project data and information.	0.00% 0	25.00% 3	25.00% 3	41.67% 5	8.33% 1	12	3.33
Share project data and information.	0.00% 0	33.33% 4	16.67% 2	41.67% 5	8.33% 1	12	3.25
Manage project data and information.	0.00% 0	16.67% 2	16.67% 2	66.67% 8	0.00% 0	12	3.50
Openness to information sharing.	25.00% 3	0.00% 0	33.33% 4	33.33% 4	8.33% 1	12	3.00
Quality of information.	8.33% 1	25.00% 3	41.67% 5	25.00% 3	0.00% 0	12	2.83
Security of confidential information.	33.33% 4	33.33% 4	16.67% 2	16.67% 2	0.00% 0	12	2.17
Credibility of the information shared.	8.33% 1	8.33% 1	66.67% 8	16.67% 2	0.00% 0	12	2.92
Trust, respect and cooperation among stakeholders.	33.33% 4	16.67% 2	16.67% 2	25.00% 3	8.33% 1	12	2.58
Share the decision making process.	16.67% 2	33.33% 4	25.00% 3	16.67% 2	8.33% 1	12	2.67
Team work.	0.00% 0	16.67% 2	50.00% 6	33.33% 4	0.00% 0	12	3.17
Incentive to work.	33.33% 4	16.67% 2	41.67% 5	8.33% 1	0.00% 0	12	2.25

Inter-disciplinary learning and skill transfer.	33.33% 4	25.00% 3	16.67% 2	16.67% 2	8.33% 1	12	2.42
Work environment.	16.67% 2	33.33% 4	33.33% 4	16.67% 2	0.00% 0	12	2.50
Reduce tensions.	41.67% 5	25.00% 3	8.33% 1	25.00% 3	0.00% 0	12	2.17
Disputes resolution.	16.67% 2	8.33% 1	41.67% 5	25.00% 3	8.33% 1	12	3.00
Discontinuity of information through project life cycle.	16.67% 2	33.33% 4	25.00% 3	16.67% 2	8.33% 1	12	2.67
Flow of information through the project life cycle.	8.33% 1	33.33% 4	16.67% 2	41.67% 5	0.00% 0	12	2.92
Early involvement of supply chain.	16.67% 2	41.67% 5	16.67% 2	25.00% 3	0.00% 0	12	2.50
Co-ordination, synchronization and sequence of the project.	0.00% 0	25.00% 3	8.33% 1	58.33% 7	8.33% 1	12	3.50

Q7 From your experience to what extent did BIM improve communications among different stakeholders at different stages of the PPP/PFI project life cycle?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

■ Not at all improved
 ■ Slightly improved
 ■ Somewhat improved
 ■ Very improved
■ Extremely improved

	Not at all improved	Slightly improved	Somewhat improved	Very improved	Extremely improved	Total	Weighted Average
(no label)	0.00% 0	25.00% 3	41.67% 5	33.33% 4	0.00% 0	12	3.08

Q8 From your experience did BIM reduce the number of conflicts at the stage of the PPP/PFI project you have been involved with?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses	
Yes	83.33%	10
No	16.67%	2
Total		12

Q9 Do you believe that BIM can encourage early involvement of stakeholders that just has stake at a later stage in order to improve project performance?

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

Answer Choices	Responses	
Yes	91.67%	11
No	8.33%	1
Total		12

Q10 Based on your experience please rank the following barriers to BIM implementation:

Answered: 12 Skipped: 0

	1	2	3	4	5	6	Total	Score
Lack of training.	0.00% 0	0.00% 0	8.33% 1	50.00% 6	25.00% 3	16.67% 2	12	2.50
Interoperability of BIM software's.	16.67% 2	8.33% 1	8.33% 1	0.00% 0	41.67% 5	25.00% 3	12	2.83
Reluctance from people toward technology.	8.33% 1	8.33% 1	33.33% 4	16.67% 2	16.67% 2	16.67% 2	12	3.25
Industry reluctance to change.	25.00% 3	33.33% 4	0.00% 0	8.33% 1	16.67% 2	16.67% 2	12	3.92
Top management support.	25.00% 3	25.00% 3	16.67% 2	16.67% 2	0.00% 0	16.67% 2	12	4.08
Initial Investment.	25.00% 3	25.00% 3	33.33% 4	8.33% 1	0.00% 0	8.33% 1	12	4.42